

Synthesis and characterization of ZnO and Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and their application in the chromium remediation studies

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Abstract : Present work describes the synthesis of zinc oxide (ZnO) and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) nanoparticles (NPs) by simple chemical reduction method. The synthesized NPs were characterized using XRD, AFM and SEM. Both ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs were used in the remediation studies to remove chromium(VI) from aqueous solution. Various process parameters such as pH, v/m ratio, contact time, initial concentration of adsorbate were evaluated to achieve optimum removal efficiency of chromium. The obtained results showed that both the NPs acted as potential adsorbents in the removal of chromium from aqueous solution; maximum removal was seen at pH 5. The contact time required to achieve the equilibrium was 60 min for ZnO and 95 min for Al₂O₃. Both the NPs demonstrated good adsorption capacity against the concentration of adsorbate thrice. Optimization of different process parameters led to 100% removal efficiency with low amount of adsorbent (150 mg of ZnO NPs and 200 mg of Al₂O₃ NPs). Reusability of the synthesized NPs was tested which suggested them to be promising adsorbents for the removal of toxic heavy metals.

Keywords : Zinc oxide NPs, alumina NPs, adsorbent, remediation, chromium(VI).

Introduction

Metal and metal oxide nanoparticles (MO NPs) represents an era of change and has given a new idea towards studies of material sciences to develop research and health related applications. From past decade MO NPs have gained lots of attention due to their applications in gas sensors, piezoelectric devices, field emission devices, power generators, ultraviolet light emitters, sensors, coatings and paints¹⁻⁶. It has been also reported that ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs are non toxic and chemically stable under different temperatures. Different methods to synthesize these MO NPs have been reported in the literature such as chemical vapour deposition⁷, thermal decomposition⁸, sol-gel methods⁹ and micro emulsion method¹⁰. But these methods are expensive compared to aqueous medium based methods which are also simple and cost effective. Rapid industrialization has led to the contamination of water sources by means of toxic heavy metals such as mercury, lead, cadmium and chromium, which originate from mining activities, petroleum refining, paint industries and leather factory's etc.¹¹. Chromium (Cr) is the chief industrial metal used in various processes and released into environment through poor storage, treatment and improper

disposal practices. Generally, chromium in environment exists in 2 different states among which hexavalent chromium [Cr^{VI}] is toxic and carcinogenic¹². Sorption technology has found increasing application in the removal of toxic metals in waste water. Many natural compounds such as algae, rubber and wood etc. have been used for remediation of toxic heavy metals from contaminated effluents and sludge which showed good adsorption capacity. However new economical and highly effective adsorbents are still urgently needed to avoid menace in tannery industries and surrounding them. In past decade nanomaterials have become more and more important due to their special properties. One of their important properties is that most of the atoms have high chemical activity and adsorption capacities to metal ions. Present study describes the synthesis of ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs using simple chemical method without any surfactants and synthesized NPs are characterized using different techniques such as XRD, AFM and SEM, further these adsorbents are used in the remediation studies of Cr from its aqueous solution. The results are presented herein for the usage of the synthesized NPs as the potential adsorbents in the removal of Cr from aqueous solution.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1A shows the XRD pattern of the synthesized ZnO NPs and all the peaks in the XRD diffractogram were indexed which matched to hexagonal ZnO (JCPDS Card No. 03-65-3411). The XRD pattern clearly showed the pure phase and strong diffraction peaks revealed that the synthesized ZnO NPs were highly crystalline. The sharp lattice constants of the synthesized nanostructures were measured to be $a = 3.2490 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.2066 \text{ \AA}$ which was in good agreement with the values of hexagonal ZnO of the space group P63mc¹³. The SEM images of synthesized ZnO NPs at different magnifications are shown in Fig. 2B and 2C and it clearly shows the formation of well dispersed ZnO NPs with the average particle size of 152.34 nm.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of synthesized ZnO NPs (A), SEM images of ZnO NPs at 300 nm (B) and 100 nm (C).

The XRD pattern of Al₂O₃ NPs (Fig. 2A) shows peaks corresponding to α -Al₂O₃ (JCPDS Card No. 83-2080). The strong diffraction peaks indicates the formation of crystalline NPs. Fig. 2B and 2C show the SEM images of Al₂O₃ NPs at different magnifications. From SEM analysis the formation of needle shaped Al₂O₃ NPs is confirmed.

The synthesized nanoparticles were used as an adsorbent for the removal of Cr from aqueous solution. Series of experiments were conducted to optimize different process parameters such as pH, v/m ratio, contact time and initial concentration.

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of synthesized Al₂O₃ NPs (A), SEM images of Al₂O₃ NPs at 10 μm (B) and 2 μm (C).

Different pHs are used to study removal efficiency of Cr^{VI} using both ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs keeping other process parameters such as contact time, adsorbent dose, agitation rate, concentration of adsorbate and temperature. Since the maximum removal efficiency (95%) was found at pH 5, so the pH 5 was maintained throughout the experiment during optimization of other process parameters. As the v/m ratio increases from 100 to 400, the removal efficiency decreases from 100 to 87.4% for ZnO NPs and 100 to 68.5% for Al₂O₃ NPs respectively. By adding different amount of synthesized NPs (50 mg to 200 mg) to Cr solution it was observed that maximum removal efficiency (100%) was achieved at 150 mg of ZnO NPs and 200 mg of Al₂O₃ NPs, so 150 mg and 200 mg of ZnO NPs and Al₂O₃ NPs were maintained throughout the experiment to study other parameters. The time required to reach equilibrium was found to be 60 min and 90 min for ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs respectively. As the initial concentration of Cr increases from 100 to 600 mg/L the removal efficiency decreases in both the cases from 100 to 82.9% for ZnO and 100 to 81% for Al₂O₃ NPs. The experiments were carried out in duplicates and the obtained results were in good agreement with $100 \pm 0.72\%$ and $100 \pm 1.2\%$ removal efficiency.

In all cases the removal efficiency (%) is calculated by the $E = (C_0 - C_1) \times 100 / C_0$, where E = efficiency of metal removal (%).

C_0 = initial concentration of Cr^{VI} (mg/L),

C_1 = final concentration of Cr^{VI} (mg/L).

Basically, the surfaces of ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs are negatively charged. When these NPs come in contact with chromium solution, chromium ions are electro-statically attracted towards the NPs surfaces and adsorbed.

Experimental

Reagents : All chemicals were purchased from Sd Fine Chemical Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai). Zinc acetate dihydrate was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Bangalore). Milli-Q water was used throughout the study period. After adsorption study all samples were filtered using 0.22 μm cellulose nitrate filter papers.

Synthesis of ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs :

500 mL of 0.01 N zinc acetate and 100 mL of 0.2 N NaOH were cooled in ice bath and then NaOH solution was added dropwise to zinc acetate dihydrate solution with stirring at 600 rpm. The resulting turbid solution was heated on water bath at 75 °C for 30 min, then settled white powder was separated followed by washing with deionized water thrice and dried overnight under room temperature.

Similar procedure was followed to synthesize Al₂O₃ NPs wherein 1.72 g of aluminum nitrate was dissolved in 470 ml of water, then 30 mL liq. ammonia was added dropwise with vigorous stirring at 550 rpm. Finally obtained powder was calcinated at 700 °C for 2 h.

Characterization of ZnO NPs :

Powder X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis was done to characterize the synthesized solid materials using Bruker D8 Advance Diffractometer (Bruker AXS, Germany) with Cu Kα radiation (k = 1.54 Å). XRD pattern of ZnO NPs was recorded over a 2-theta range of 10–90°. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) analysis was done using a Carl Zeiss SEM Instrument attached to EVO MA 15 (Oxford Instrument) after sprinkling solid powder samples on the adhesive carbon tape which was supported on the metallic disc.

Removal of Cr by ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs :

Effect of pH on removal efficiency :

In order to study the effect of pH, 100 ppm Cr solution was prepared and from which 20 ml of solution was taken into four different reaction tubes and the pH was adjusted to 3, 4, 5 and 6 respectively. 100 mg of ZnO NPs were added to each bottle and kept for spinning at 50

Fig. 3. Removal efficiency of Cr using ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs against pH (A), v/m ratio (B), contact time (C) and initial concentration of Cr (D).

rpm for 4 h in a rotospin. After spinning, the solution was filtered and then concentration of Cr was estimated by AAS. Another set of experiments was carried out with Al₂O₃ NPs for the removal of chromium from its aqueous solution.

Effect of v/m ratio on removal efficiency :

20 ml of Cr solution (100 ppm) was taken into four different reaction tubes and the pH was adjusted to 5. The varying amounts of ZnO NPs were added i.e. 50, 100, 150 and 200 mg. Then the bottles were spinned at 50 rpm for 4 h, then solutions were filtered and the equilibrium Zn concentration was quantified using AAS analysis. Similarly another set of experiments was carried out with varying amount of Al₂O₃ NPs.

Effect of contact time on removal of Cr :

20 ml of Cr solution (100 ppm) was taken into five different reaction tubes and the pH was adjusted to 5 in each one of them. Then 150 mg of ZnO NPs were added to each bottle. The bottles were kept for spinning at 50 rpm for 2, 4, 8, 18 and 24 h, then solutions were filtered and AAS analysis was carried out. In case of Al₂O₃ NPs 200 mg were added in all the tubes.

Effect of initial concentration on removal efficiency :

100, 200, 400 and 600 ppm of the Cr solutions were prepared and from which 20 ml of each solution was taken into four different reagent bottles and the pH was

adjusted to 5. 150 mg of ZnO NPs were added to each bottle. Then these bottles were kept for spinning at 50 rpm for 4 h, then solutions were filtered and subjected to AAS. Similar reaction with 200 mg of Al₂O₃ NPs was carried out.

Conclusion

Synthesis of ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs was achieved by simple chemical reduction without using any stabilizing agents. XRD results showed that the synthesized ZnO NPs were highly crystalline and formation of α -Al₂O₃ NPs. SEM analysis revealed the formation of well dispersed ZnO NPs and Al₂O₃ NPs with rod shaped morphology. Further synthesized ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs were used as adsorbent in Cr remediation studies; maximum removal was found to happen at pH 5. For the studies of v/m ratio, highest removal efficiency was optimized at 150 and 200 (150 mg of ZnO NPs and 200 mg of Al₂O₃ NPs in 20 mL Cr solution). Using contact time as the parameter it was found that, the contact time required to achieve the equilibrium was found to be 60 min and 95 min for ZnO and Al₂O₃ NPs respectively. In conclusion, the synthesized NPs can be effectively used as potential adsorbent to remove Cr^{VI} from waste water.

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